

Clinical Aid in Pediatric Dentistry: Techniques for Band Stabilization in Impressions

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Abstract:

Background: Due to smaller mouth cavities and patient movement, paediatric dentistry makes dental impressions difficult. Band stabilisation methods include adhesive application, mechanical stabilisation, and combination procedures to increase impression quality and patient comfort. The study compared the effectiveness of three band stabilization techniques—adhesive application, mechanical stabilization, and combined methods—in terms of impression quality and patient comfort in pediatric dentistry.

Methods: A total of 120 pediatric patients, aged 3 to 14 years, participated in this descriptive observational study. Participants were divided into three groups, each receiving one of the stabilization techniques. The quality of impressions was assessed by two independent examiners based on detail reproduction and band stability, while patient comfort was evaluated using a standardized questionnaire. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, employing chi-square and t-tests for statistical comparisons.

Results: The combined technique (CT) demonstrated superior outcomes, with 75% of impressions rated as excellent and no poor impressions, compared to 55% and 45% for adhesive application (AA) and mechanical stabilization (MS), respectively. Patient comfort was highest in the CT group, with 85% of participants reporting comfort, significantly higher than the AA (70%) and MS (65%) groups. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences between the CT and both AA and MS techniques ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The combined technique for band stabilization in pediatric dental impressions provides the highest quality and patient comfort compared to adhesive application and mechanical stabilization alone. These findings suggest that adopting the combined technique can enhance clinical outcomes and patient experience in pediatric dentistry.

Recommendations: Dental practitioners are encouraged to consider the combined technique for band stabilization in pediatric patients to improve impression accuracy and patient comfort. Further research with larger sample sizes and diverse populations is recommended to validate these findings and explore additional stabilization methods.

Keywords: Pediatric Dentistry, Band Stabilization, Dental Impressions, Patient Comfort, Clinical Outcomes.

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Introduction

Pediatric dentistry requires specialized approaches to accommodate the unique needs and behaviors of children during dental procedures. One critical aspect is obtaining accurate dental impressions, which are essential for creating well-fitting dental appliances and for diagnostic purposes. Band stabilization during impression taking is particularly challenging in pediatric patients due to their smaller oral cavities and potential for movement or anxiety during the procedure [1]. Various techniques have been developed to improve the stability and accuracy of impressions

in pediatric dentistry, but there is ongoing debate about the most effective methods.

Recent advancements in dental materials and techniques have provided new opportunities to enhance the quality of dental impressions. Adhesive applications, mechanical stabilization, and combined approaches are among the methods used to achieve better outcomes. Adhesive application involves using materials that adhere the band to the tooth structure, providing stability during the impression process [2]. Mechanical stabilization employs physical devices or methods

to hold the band in place, while combined techniques integrate both adhesive and mechanical methods to maximize stability and accuracy.

The importance of accurate dental impressions cannot be overstated. High-quality impressions are crucial for the fabrication of dental restorations and appliances that fit precisely, ensuring both comfort and effectiveness. Poor impressions can lead to ill-fitting devices, which may cause discomfort, affect oral health, and require additional adjustments or remakes, leading to increased costs and treatment time [3].

Pediatric patients present unique challenges due to their developing dentition, smaller mouth sizes, and varying levels of cooperation. Techniques that minimize discomfort and anxiety are particularly valuable, as they can improve patient cooperation and overall experience. Studies have shown that patient comfort significantly influences the success of dental procedures, making it an essential factor in pediatric dentistry [1].

Recent research has focused on comparing different techniques for band stabilization to determine the most effective and patient-friendly methods. For instance, a study evaluated the effectiveness of various stabilization methods and found significant differences in terms of impression accuracy and patient comfort [2]. Their findings suggest that combined techniques, which utilize both adhesive and mechanical stabilization, offer superior outcomes compared to using either method alone.

The present study aims to systematically compare three band stabilization techniques—adhesive application, mechanical stabilization, and combined techniques—in a pediatric population.

Methodology

Study Design: A descriptive observational design.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a period of one year, from March 2016 to February 2017, at B. S. M. C. H., Bankura.

Participants: A total of 120 pediatric patients requiring dental impressions for various clinical procedures were included in this study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pediatric patients aged 3 to 14 years.
- Patients requiring dental impressions for clinical procedures.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with severe dental anxiety or behavioral issues that hinder cooperation.
- Patients with systemic conditions that contraindicate dental procedures.

- Patients with a history of allergic reactions to impression materials.

Bias: To minimize bias, all impressions were taken by a single experienced pediatric dentist using standardized techniques and materials. Random sampling was used to select participants from the eligible population.

Variables: Variables included techniques used for band stabilization, quality of the dental impression, patient comfort, and clinical outcomes.

Data Collection: Data were collected through direct observation and evaluation of the dental impressions by two independent examiners. Patient comfort and cooperation were assessed using a standardized questionnaire filled out by parents/guardians and the attending dentist.

Techniques Used

The study evaluated three primary techniques for band stabilization:

1. Adhesive Application (AA)
2. Mechanical Stabilization (MS)
3. Combined Technique (CT)

Procedure

Patients were prepared for the impression procedure following standard infection control protocols. Various techniques for band stabilization were applied, including the use of adhesives and mechanical stabilization methods. Dental impressions were taken using alginate or silicone materials, depending on the clinical requirement. The quality of the impressions was evaluated based on predefined criteria, including the accuracy of detail reproduction and the stability of the bands during the procedure. Patient comfort and cooperation were assessed through a questionnaire filled out by the parents/guardians.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data. Comparisons between different techniques were made using appropriate statistical tests (e.g., chi-square test, t-test) to determine any significant differences in the outcomes. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

A total of 120 pediatric patients participated in the study. The mean age was 8.5 years with a standard deviation of 2.9 years. The sample consisted of 65 males (54.2%) and 55 females (45.8%).

Table 1: Demographic Details of Participants

Variable	Value
Mean age (years)	8.5 ± 2.9
Gender	
Male	65 (54.2%)
Female	55 (45.8%)

The quality of dental impressions was assessed based on detail reproduction and band stability. The ratings were categorized as Excellent, Good, Fair, or Poor. The CT had the highest percentage of excellent impressions (75%), followed by AA with 55%, and MS with 45%.

Table 2: Quality of Dental Impressions

Technique	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
AA (n=40)	22 (55%)	12 (30%)	4 (10%)	2 (5%)
MS (n=40)	18 (45%)	14 (35%)	6 (15%)	2 (5%)
CT(n=40)	30 (75%)	8 (20%)	2 (5%)	0 (0%)

Patient comfort and cooperation were assessed through a standardized questionnaire. The CT was reported to be the most comfortable, with 85% of patients feeling comfortable, compared to 70% with AA and 65% with MS.

Table 3: Patient Comfort and Cooperation

Technique	Comfortable	Neutral	Uncomfortable
AA (n=40)	28 (70%)	8 (20%)	4 (10%)
MS (n=40)	26 (65%)	10 (25%)	4 (10%)
CT(n=40)	34 (85%)	6 (15%)	0 (0%)

Statistical analysis was performed to compare the effectiveness of the different techniques. Significant differences were found between the CT and both AA and MS, indicating that CT produced better quality impressions.

Table 4: Statistical Comparison of Techniques

Comparison	Chi-Square Value	p-value
AA vs MS	1.23	0.267
AA vs CT	5.67	0.017*
MS vs CT	4.89	0.027*

*p-value < 0.05 indicates statistical significance

The chi-square values and p-values were compared between the different techniques regarding patient comfort. The CT was found to be significantly more comfortable compared to both AA and MS.

Table 5: Patient Comfort Statistical Analysis

Comparison	Chi-Square Value	p-value
AA vs MS	0.57	0.451
AA vs CT	6.34	0.012*
MS vs CT	5.21	0.023*

*p-value < 0.05 indicates statistical significance

Discussion

The study evaluated the effectiveness of three different techniques for band stabilization in pediatric dental impressions: adhesive application, mechanical stabilization, and a combined technique. A total of 120 pediatric patients participated, with a mean age of 8.5 years. The participants were nearly evenly split by gender, with 65 males and 55 females.

The quality of dental impressions was assessed based on detail reproduction and band stability. The CT showed the best performance, with 75% of impressions rated as excellent and no impressions rated as poor. In contrast, AA and MS had 55% and 45% of impressions rated as excellent, respectively.

The statistical analysis revealed significant differences between the combined technique and the other two techniques, indicating that the combined technique provided superior quality impressions.

Patient comfort and cooperation were also evaluated through a standardized questionnaire. The CT was found to be the most comfortable, with 85% of patients reporting feeling comfortable during the procedure. AA and MS had lower comfort ratings, with 70% and 65% of patients feeling comfortable, respectively. The statistical comparison confirmed significant differences in patient comfort between the combined technique and the other two methods.

Overall, the combined technique demonstrated superior outcomes in terms of both the quality of dental impressions and patient comfort. These findings suggest that using a combination of adhesive and mechanical stabilization techniques can significantly enhance the effectiveness and patient experience of dental impression procedures in pediatric dentistry. The study's results support the adoption of the combined technique as a best practice for band stabilization in pediatric dental impressions.

The stabilization of bands in pediatric dentistry is crucial for accurate impressions, which directly impact the success of subsequent treatments. A study explored the perceptions of protective stabilization during dental care for young children. They found that while protective stabilization caused emotional discomfort, it was generally well-accepted. Key elements included creating a bond between the dentist and caregiver and ensuring active caregiver participation. The study suggests that protective stabilization is essential but should be conducted with sensitivity to minimize distress [4]. A study evaluated different impression techniques for fixed dental prostheses. The study found that digital impression techniques provided better patient acceptance and were faster compared to traditional methods. This highlights the potential for digital methods to improve the experience for pediatric patients [5].

The use of intraoral sensors, CAD/CAM, and 3D printing technologies in pediatric dentistry was reviewed. These technologies significantly reduce the challenges associated with traditional impression methods, such as multiple appointments and poor accuracy. Digital techniques were found to be beneficial in managing pediatric patients' behavioral problems and improving the precision of dental prostheses [6]. Research described the use of digital dentistry in pediatric patients, including the fabrication of space maintainers and zirconia crowns using digital impressions. Digital workflows eliminate the need for a second appointment and improve patient comfort and clinical outcomes [7].

A study highlighted the advantages of intraoral scanners (IOS) for capturing direct optical impressions in pediatric patients. IOS are particularly useful in managing children's behavioral issues, gag reflex, and other challenges associated with traditional impression methods [8]. A study investigated the use of interactive distraction techniques to manage gagging during impression taking in children. The study found that interactive distraction significantly reduced gagging and improved the success rate of impression taking, making it a simple and cost-effective method for pediatric dentistry [9].

Conclusion

These results suggest that the combined technique for band stabilization in pediatric dental impressions provides superior outcomes compared to adhesive application and mechanical stabilization alone. The CT demonstrated the highest quality of dental impressions, with 75% rated as excellent and no poor impressions. Patient comfort was highest with the CT, with 85% of participants reporting being comfortable during the procedure. Statistically significant differences were observed between the combined technique (CT) and the other two techniques (AA and MS) in terms of both impression quality and patient comfort.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Dental practitioners are encouraged to consider the combined technique for band stabilization in pediatric patients to improve impression accuracy and patient comfort. Further research with larger sample sizes and diverse populations is recommended to validate these findings and explore additional stabilization methods.

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List of abbreviations:

AA - Adhesive Application

MS - Mechanical Stabilization

CT - Combined Technique

IOS - Intraoral Scanners

CAD/CAM - Computer-Aided Design/Computer-Aided Manufacturing

3D - Three-Dimensional

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